

Background: Continuous respiratory monitoring is crucial for early disease detection, chronic disease management, and post-surgical recovery. Wearable solutions offer non-invasive and mobile alternatives to conventional methods, improving accessibility and patient comfort.

Objective: This study aims to develop and validate a smart textile singlet equipped with IMU sensors for respiratory monitoring. The hypothesis is that the IMU-based system achieves comparable accuracy to a motion capture system (Vicon) in measuring breathing cycle duration.

Methods: A pilot study was conducted with one subject performing controlled breathing exercises while being monitored by both an IMU-based system and Vicon. The Z-axis angular velocity was analyzed, differentiated, and peak detection was applied to estimate breathing cycle duration. The results were validated using intrasubject correlation and a paired T-test.

Results: The IMU-based system showed a high intrasubject correlation (ICC = 0.72) with Vicon, with a mean difference of 0.007 seconds. The paired T-test indicated no significant difference ($p = 0.957$) between the two methods, confirming the reliability of the proposed approach.

Implication for research and/or (healthcare) practice: These results demonstrate the potential of IMU-equipped smart textiles for continuous respiratory monitoring in clinical and everyday applications. The non-invasive nature of the system supports long-term usability. Future work will focus on refining the algorithm, expanding the dataset, and addressing motion artifacts and physiological variability.